

Statistical review of *Synairgen announces positive results from trial of SNG001 in hospitalised COVID-19 patients*

July 20th, 2020

The following review has been prepared in collaboration with members of the MRC-NIHR Trials Methodology Research Partnership¹. The reviewers named above, and other, unnamed discussants of the paper, are all qualified statisticians with experience in clinical trials. Our objective is to provide a rapid review of publications, preprints and protocols from clinical trials of COVID-19 treatments, independent of journal specific review processes. We aim to provide timely, constructive, focused, clear advice aimed at improving both the research outputs under review, as well as future studies. Given our collective expertise (clinical trial statistics) our reviews focus on the designs of the trials and other statistical content (methods, presentation and accuracy of results, inferences). This review reflects the expert opinions of the named authors, and does not imply endorsement by the MRC-NIHR Trials Methodology Research Partnership, its wider membership, or any other organisation.

Here we review *Synairgen announces positive results from trial of SNG001 in hospitalised COVID-19 patients*, by Marketing Hacks et al². The press released on July 20th on the Twitter, and is available at:

<https://www.synairgen.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/200720-Synairgen-announces-positive-results-from-trial-of-SNG001-in-hospitalised-COVID-19-patients.pdf>

Overall, this was A PRESS RELEASE AND NOBODY HAS ANY IDEA WHAT IT MEANS WITHOUT AN ACCOMPANYING FULL REPORT OF THE TRIAL RESULTS THAT CAN BE EVALUATED BY INDEPENDENT EXPERTS.

CONSORT CHECKLIST

As if.